

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Eleven

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 11:0 For the choir director. A <i>Psalm</i> of David.</p> <p>¹ In the LORD I take refuge; How can you say to my soul, "Flee as a bird to your mountain; ² For, behold, the wicked bend the bow, They make ready their arrow upon the string To shoot in darkness at the upright in heart. ³ If the foundations are destroyed, What can the righteous do?"</p> <p>Psa. 11:4 The LORD is in His holy temple; the LORD'S throne is in Heaven; His eyes behold, His eyelids test the sons of men. ⁵ The LORD tests the righteous and the wicked, And the one who loves violence His soul hates. ⁶ Upon the wicked He will rain snares; Fire and brimstone and burning wind will be the portion of their cup. ⁷ For the LORD is righteous, He loves righteousness; The upright will behold His face.</p>	<p>Psa. 11:1 לְמַנְצֵחַת לְדָוִד בְּיְהוָה תְּסִיִּתִי אֵיךְ תֹּאמְרוּ לְנַפְשִׁי נִוְדוּ [נִוְדִי] תִּרְכָּם צַפּוֹר : ² כִּי הִנֵּה הֲרִשְׁעִים יִדְרֹכֹון קִשְׁת כּוֹנְנֵו חֲצָם עַל-יֵתֶר לִירוֹת בְּמוֹ-אֶפֶל לְיִשְׂרָאֵל : ³ כִּי הַשָּׂתוֹת יִהְרָסוּן צִדִיק מֵה- פֶּעַל : ⁴ יְהוָה אֲבֵהִיכֹל קִדְשׁוֹ יְהוָה בַּשָּׁמַיִם כָּסְאוֹ עֵינָיו יִתְּזוּ עַבְעֵפָיו יִבְחֲנוּ בְּנֵי אָדָם : ⁵ יְהוָה צִדִיק יִבְחֵן וְרָשָׁע וְאֲתֵב חֲמָס שִׁנְאָה נִפְשׁוֹ : ⁶ יִמְטֵר עַל- רָשָׁעִים פָּתִים אֵשׁ וְגַפְרִית וְרוּחַ זֶלְעָפוֹת מְנַת כּוֹסָם : ⁷ כִּי- צִדִיק יְהוָה צְדָקוֹת אֲתֵב יִשְׂר יִתְּזוּ פְּנֵימוֹ :</p>

Targum

Psa. 11:1 A hymn of David. In the word of the LORD I have hoped; how do you say to my soul, wander to the mountain like a bird? ² For behold, the wicked bend the bow, fixing their arrows on the string to shoot in darkness at the firm of heart. ³ For if the foundations are shattered, why did the virtuous do good? ⁴ The LORD is in his temple; God's throne is in the highest heavens; his eyes see, his eyelids examine, the sons of men. ⁵ God examines the righteous, but his soul hates the wicked and those who love rapacity. ⁶ He will bring down rains of retribution on the wicked, coals of fire and brimstone; a violent storm-wind is the portion of their cup. ⁷ For the LORD is righteous, he loves righteousness, the honest man will look upon his countenance.

Interlinear

Psa. 11:0	For	the	choir	director	A	Psalm	of	David	
Key									
Lex									
PrtSpeech									
Psa. 11:1	In	the	Lord	I	take				
Key			H3068		H2620				
Lex			יהוה		קָחָה				
PrtSpeech			Noun		Verb				
refuge	How	can	you	say	to	my	soul		
H2620	H0349			H0559			H5315		
קָחָה	אֵיךְ			אָמַר			נַפְשׁ		
Verb	Part.			Verb			Noun		
Flee	as	a	bird	to	your	mountain			
H5110			H6833			H2022			
נָדַד			צִפּוֹר			הַר			
Verb			Noun			Noun			
Psa. 11:2	For	behold	the	wicked					
Key		H2009		H7563					
Lex		הִנֵּה		רָשָׁע					
PrtSpeech		Part.		Adj.					
bend	the	bow	They	make					
H1869		H7198		H3559					
דָּבַד		קִשָּׁת		פָּוַן					
Verb		Noun		Verb					
ready	their	arrow	upon	the	string	To	shoot	in	darkness
H3559		H2671			H3499b		H3384		H0652
פָּוַן		חֵץ			יִתָּר		יָרָה		אֶפֶל
Verb		Noun			Noun		Verb		Noun
at	the	upright	in	heart					
		H3477		H3820					
		יָשָׁר		לֵב					
		Adj.		Noun					
Psa. 11:3		If	the	foundations	are	destroyed			
Key		H3588		H8356		H2040			

Lex PrtSpeech		כִּי Part.		שָׁתָה Noun		הָרַם Verb		
What H4100 מָה Pron.	can	the	righteous H6662 צַדִּיק Adj.	do H6466 פָּעַל Verb				
Psa. 11:4 Key Lex PrtSpeech		The	Lord H3068 יְהוָה Noun	is	in	His		
holy H6944 קֹדֶשׁ Noun	temple H1964 הַיְכָל Noun	the	Lord's H3068 יְהוָה Noun	throne H3678 כִּסֵּא Noun	is	in	heaven H8064 שָׁמַיִם Noun	
His H5869 עַיִן Noun	eyes	behold H2372 הִנֵּה Verb	His	eyelids H6079 עַפְעָרַי Noun	test H0974 בָּחַן Verb			
the	sons H1121 בָּנִים Noun	of	men H0120 אָדָם Noun					
Psa. 11:5 Key Lex PrtSpeech		The	Lord H3068 יְהוָה Noun	tests H0974 בָּחַן Verb	the			
righteous H6662 צַדִּיק Adj.	and	the	wicked H7563 רָשָׁע Adj.	And	the	one	who	loves H0157 אָהַב Verb
violence H2555 הַמָּוֶט Noun	His	soul H5315 נַפְשׁוֹ Noun	hates H8130 שָׂנֵא Verb					

Psa. 11:6 Key Lex PrtSpeech	Upon	the	wicked H7563 רָשָׁע Adj.	He	will	rain H4305 מָטַר Verb		
snares H6341a פֶּה Noun	Fire H0784 אֵשׁ Noun	and	brimstone H1614 נְפֹתִית Noun	and				
burning H2152 וּלְעֹפֶה Noun	wind H7307 רוּחַ Noun	will	be	the	portion H4521 מִנְתָּה Noun	of	their	cup H3563a כּוּס Noun
Psa. 11:7 Key Lex PrtSpeech	For	the	Lord H3068 יְהוָה Noun	is	righteous H6662 צַדִּיק Adj.			
He	loves H0157 אָהַב Verb	righteousness H6666 צְדָקָה Noun	The					
upright H3477 יָשָׁר Adj.	will	behold H2372 הִזָּה Verb	His	face H6440 פָּנִים Noun				

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 11:0 For the choir director. A <i>Psalm</i> of David.</p> <p>¹ In the LORD I take refuge; How can you say to my soul, "Flee as a bird to your mountain;</p>	<p>לְמַנְצֵחַת לְדָוִד בְּיַהֲוָה וְתַסִּיִּתִי אֵיךְ תֹּאמְרוּ לְנַפְשִׁי נִוְדוּ [נִוְדוּרִי] תִּרְכָּם צְפוּר</p>

Verse Analysis

This Psalm is a sequel to Psalm 10 because it tries to answer why wicked people prosper while the righteous suffer.

A mountain is a symbol of stability. The bird denotes something unstable and easily moveable. The Sage Rashi said that David wrote this Psalm when he was fleeing from Saul's men. They were trying to capture David to kill him. So David hid in the caves in the mountains to elude the men.

נִוְדוּ (nudu) is in the plural form. The verb means "to flee." Why did David use the plural form of the verb? The Sage Radak said that the men wanting to kill David wanted his body and his soul destroyed. If David's soul was destroyed, then he could not find rest in Heaven. His existence would have been wiped out on Earth and in Heaven.

"Flee for your mountain is a bird" is an interesting phrase. The mountain symbolizes stability, and for David, that stability was His faith and trust in the LORD. Why would the LORD tell Him that his faith was like a bird, which means that it was unstable? To fully grasp this, the concept of where the LORD's influence on Earth in David's day must be examined. The people of David's day believed that the LORD's influence was only in Eretz Israel (the land of Israel). Therefore, David was surprised that the LORD was telling him to leave Eretz Israel. David was confused that the LORD would tell him to leave His presence. However, the LORD knew that if David stayed inside the borders of Eretz Israel that Saul's men would capture and kill him. Therefore, the verse is saying that the security of the LORD was not secure for David. Saul's men were going to find him and kill him.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the conductor, a psalm of David. In the LORD, I took refuge from my evil enemies. Why, LORD, would you tell me to leave Eretz Israel and your protection?

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² For, behold, the wicked bend the bow, They make ready their arrow upon the string To shoot in darkness at the upright in heart.</p>	<p>² כִּי תִנֶּה הַרְשָׁעִים יְדֵי כּוֹחַ קָשָׁת כּוֹנְנֵי תַצֵּם עַל-יָתֵד לִירוֹת בְּמוֹ-אֶפֶל לְיֹשְׁרֵי-לֵב :</p>

Verse Analysis

Wicked people are quick and ready to kill the righteous. They will shoot an arrow to kill the righteous even if they cannot see them. They hate everything proper and good in the world.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Wicked people are always ready to kill a righteous person.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
3 If the foundations are destroyed, What can the righteous do?"	כִּי הִשָּׁתַׁתּוּת יְהוָה סִוֵּן צְדִיק מֵ-3 פְּעַל :

Verse Analysis

What are the foundations? The LORD's moral and ethical order is the foundation of the Universe. However, what happens if the foundation becomes rotten? This situation allows evil and wickedness to triumph. There is nothing to stop them. The pillars of justice and law will stop evil, but not when they are either removed from society or the enforces of justice and law decide not to enforce them anymore.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

When justice and law are removed from your creation LORD, what can a righteous man do to restore them?

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 11:4 The LORD is in His holy temple; the LORD'S throne is in Heaven; His eyes behold, His eyelids test the sons of men.</p>	<p>יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ יְהוָה בְּשָׁמַיִם כִּסֵּאוֹ עֵינָיו יַחֲזִי עַפְעָפִיו יִבְחֲנוּ בְּנֵי אָדָם :</p>

Verse Analysis

כִּסֵּה (keeseh) – means "throne." It also denotes that the LORD's throne is more than just a throne in the Heavens. The entire Universe is a part of the LORD's throne. Since the LORD retracted to create the Universe (from the Book of Creation), the Universe is always a part of the LORD. Therefore, the LORD's throne encompasses everything.

The LORD sees everything, the all-seeing eye. The eyelids remind humans that they can do things that do not get recognized immediately by the LORD, thus closing the eyelids. However, the eyelids do open, and the LORD will see everything. Therefore, it is a fallacy to think that the LORD's eyelids close at any time. They are always open and always watching what is happening in His creation.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD resides on His throne in Heaven and sees everything all the time.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ The LORD tests the righteous and the wicked, And the one who loves violence His soul hates.</p>	<p>יְהוָה צֹדֵיק יִבְחֵן וְרָשָׁע וְאַתָּה תִּמְסֵ שִׁנְאָה נַפְשׁוֹ :</p>

Verse Analysis

It always appears odd that the LORD test the righteous. Testing the wicked makes sense because the LORD wants to see if the wicked person turns away from their wicked ways. Why constantly test the righteous? The Sages tell us that the more righteous one is, the more intense the testing from the LORD. For example, Abraham proved his love for the LORD when he destroyed his father's idols. He showed the LORD his love on many other occasions. However, the LORD tested Abraham no less than ten times. The thought is that the righteous are tested to increase their righteousness. The LORD prepares the righteous for the world to come (Heaven). Each test to a righteous person is a lesson that the LORD wants them to learn before He will allow the person to enter Heaven. The LORD dispenses with wicked people because it is known that the wicked person will not change. Therefore, why would the LORD want to deal with such a person?

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD constantly is testing the righteous and the wicked. The wicked person who decides to remain wicked the LORD will not allow in Heaven.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁶ Upon the wicked He will rain snares; Fire and brimstone and burning wind will be the portion of their cup.</p>	<p>יִמְטֵר עַל־רְשָׁעִים פְּתָיִם אֵשׁ וְגַבְרִית וְרוּחַ זֶלְעָפוֹת מִנְּת כּוֹסָם :</p>

Verse Analysis

יִמְטֵר (yametare) - this word means "rain." However, it denotes more than just rain. It denotes anything that comes from the LORD's Heaven.

פְּתָיִם (pacheem) – this word means "traps." David was referring to the victims of unsuspecting traps that catch the feet. There are many traps that the LORD can send, but also there are traps that society develops. For example, prosperity can turn a person's heart away from charity. The desire to have as many valuables as possible can pollute the mind. Then, the person forgets about the poor people.

The LORD sends fire, brimstone, and wind to wicked people. An example is what the LORD sent to Sodom and Gemorrah. When Lot and his family evacuated the city, the LORD sent fire, brimstone and wind to destroy the wicked city.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He sends traps for wicked people; fire, brimstone, and wind are sent to the lover of violence whom the LORD despises.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 For the LORD is righteous, He loves righteousness; The upright will behold His face.	כִּי־צַדִּיק יִהְיֶה צְדָקוֹת אֱהָב יִשָּׂר יִתְּנוּ פְּנֵיהֶם :

Verse Analysis

There are many times throughout history that the LORD's way does not make any sense to humans. For example, David did not understand why the LORD told him to leave Eretz Israel. David did not understand that the LORD is the LORD of all creation, which means that no matter where David went on the Earth, the LORD was with him. So, to David, the LORD's command to leave Eretz Israel seemed crazy. However, David did obey the LORD and understood that it is unnecessary to comprehend what the LORD wants a person to do.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the LORD is righteous, He loves righteous people; He will show His love to the righteous.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the conductor, a psalm of David. In the LORD, I took refuge from my evil enemies.

Why, LORD, would you tell me to leave Eretz Israel and your protection?

Wicked people are always ready to kill a righteous person.

When justice and law are removed from your creation LORD, what can a righteous man do to restore them.

The LORD resides on His throne in Heaven and sees everything all the time.

The LORD constantly is testing the righteous and the wicked. The wicked person who decides to remain wicked the LORD will not allow in Heaven.

He sends traps for wicked people; fire, brimstone, and wind are sent to the lover of violence whom the LORD despises.

For the LORD is righteous, He loves righteous people; He will show His love to the righteous.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

